

Construction of metal template polymer with covalently bound dithizone

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Dithizone complexes of Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} have been attached to a copolymer of styrene and acrylic acid which are then crosslinked. The metal ions are leached out leaving the ligand attached to the polymeric matrix. Absorption capacity of various metal ions in these polymeric ligands have been measured to evaluate the extent of template effect generated.

Chelating resins have become important tools in recent years for removal of metal ions from aqueous solutions¹. Various types of multidentate ligands have thus been introduced into a variety of network polymers². Although these chelating resins take up almost all transition metal ions in high yield, they mostly do not have sufficient selectivity of metal ion. A particular metal ion can be removed by controlling the pH of aqueous solution. But this method is not practical because pH control of the bulk aqueous phase and drainage in large quantities are difficult. To overcome this problem new ideas are being developed to generate ion specific polymeric ligand systems, the so called template polymeric ligand matrix. In these cases, the polymer-ligand chain is maintained at an optimal conformation for the coordination sphere of a particular metal ion so that the particular metal ion is absorbed preferentially³⁻⁶.

A chelating sorbent loaded with dithizone has been thought useful, because dithizone is one of the most versatile chelating reagents forming complexes with heavy metals⁷. Dithizone chelating resins have thus been prepared by deposition of dithizone on polyurethane foam⁸ and polystyrene beads⁹ and used for preconcentration of mercury from sea water, but the recovery is not always good enough, because of instability of sorbents. Dithizone deposited on polyurethane foam has also been used as a sorbent for collection of silver and mercury and detection of zinc and lead¹⁰.

A chelating sorbent loaded with dithizone in styrene-divinylbenzene (DVB) copolymer matrix was applied to determine copper and lead in river water and of silver in electrolytic copper¹¹. Dithizone-anchored-poly(vinylpyridine) has been used as a chelating resin for the preconcentration and separation of Au^{III} from Pt^{II} , Cu^{II} and Hg^{II} ¹².

Our effort to prepare ion specific template sites by physical entrapment of oriented dithizone in polymeric matrices has been reported earlier⁵. In the present work, dithizone in

a particular pattern has been bonded covalently to a rigid crosslinked polymeric matrix. The idea is to fix a metal chelate complex covalently through a functional group in the ligand moiety into a rigid crosslinked polymer so that when the metal ion is removed it leaves the ligand bound to the polymeric matrix in a cavity more compatible to the particular metal ion. This may provide selective absorption independent or less dependent on equilibrium constant. Four template polymers are made with Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} and Ni^{II} ions, and the selectivity of each has been measured. The synthetic procedure is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

Metal ion absorption capacities of different template polymeric ligand matrices are listed in Table 1. From the data, it is clear that the amount of metal ions absorbed by a

Table 1. Metal absorption capacities of different metal template polymeric ligand matrices using ethylene glycol as crosslinking agent

Template polymer type	Metal ions absorbed, mmol g ⁻¹			
	Cu ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Ni ^{II}
Cu-template	0.102	0.078	0.068	0.058
Co-template	0.088	0.090	0.070	0.064
Zn-template	0.064	0.056	0.072	0.052
Ni-template	0.082	0.064	0.044	0.090

polymeric ligand is maximum for the metal ion from which the template is formed irrespective of the stability constant. Quantities of other metal ions absorbed are lower even when their stability constants are higher. A comparative picture is shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Selectivity curve showing template effect

The metal ions chosen have comparable ionic radii but different electronic configurations. It is therefore, imperative, that the specificity observed was not totally dependent on hole size but also on the frozen geometry and/or conformation of the ligand in the solid polymeric matrix⁴⁻⁶.

It is observed that the percentage of attached ligand available for complexation varies from metal to metal and obviously proportional to their stability constants.

Moreover, a considerable extent of the attached ligand

Fig. 2. Bar chart showing template effect

is structurally restrained from absorbing metal ion due to collapse of the molecules from solution to solid state on crosslinking. This may be expected considering the hydrophobic nature of the base polymer and situation of ligand and metal ion in different phases.

Table 2. Ligand availability of various polymer

Template polymer type	% Nitrogen by weight	Dithizone content mmol g ⁻¹	Template metal absorption mmol g ⁻¹	Mole % ligand available to template metal	Stability constant log K
Cu-template	1.51	0.270	0.102	75.6	19.18
Co-template	1.54	0.275	0.090	65.4	13.97
Zn-template	1.26	0.225	0.072	64.0	12.96
Ni-template	1.65	0.295	0.090	61.0	9.55

From the results it may be concluded that significant memory or template effect could be achieved by the method presented though it is not very high. It has also been observed that the metal absorbing capacity does not decrease on repeated use of the same polymer nor any ligand leached

Table 3. Reactivity of the polymeric ligands with various metal ions

Template polymer type	Mole % ligand available to metal ion			
	Cu ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Ni ^{II}
Cu-template	75.0	57.8	50.4	43.0
Co-template	64.0	65.4	50.9	46.5
Zn-template	56.0	49.7	64.0	46.2
Ni-template	55.6	43.4	29.8	61.0

out in the experimental condition. By altering the crosslinking agent and the distance between the active sites of the ligand and main chain backbone it may be possible to enhance the specificity which is a matter of our further study.

Experimental

Synthesis of styrene-acrylic acid copolymer : Freshly distilled styrene (20 ml) and acrylic acid (10 ml) in benzene (40 ml) was polymerized with benzoyl peroxide (0.1 g) in nitrogen atmosphere at 70° for 4 h. The resulting polymer was precipitated in petroleum ether (b.p. 40°–60°) and purified by repeated precipitation from tetrahydrofuran solution followed by drying in a vacuum oven at 60°.

Determination of acrylic acid content in the copolymer : The percentage of acrylic acid in the copolymer was determined by IR spectroscopy with propionic acid as the reference standard. The acrylic acid content in the copolymer was found to be 30 mole percent.

Preparation of acid chloride of the copolymer : The copolymer (2 g) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (15 ml) for 2–3 h. The excess thionyl chloride was then removed by distillation and the polymer was purified by repeated precipitation with dry hexane from a solution of dry tetrahydrofuran.

Preparation of metal dithizone complexes : Four metal complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II} were prepared by reacting the metal ions and dithizone in 1 : 2 mole ratio. Metal salts (chlorides or nitrates) were taken in aqueous solution and dithizone in chloroform. The mixture was stirred vigorously and separated. The chloroform layer containing the complex was separated and washed with very dilute aqueous ammonia till the orange colour of ammonia-dithizone disappeared. The chloroform layer was evaporated, dried, and the complexes recrystallised from chloroform.

Spectroscopic absorption data confirmed the formation of the complexes.

Preparation of template polymeric ligand matrix using ethylene glycol : The polymer acid chloride (2 g) in tetrahydrofuran (25 ml) was treated with dithizone-metal complex (0.2 g) in presence of dry distilled pyridine (2 ml) and stirred vigorously for 0.5 h, followed by addition of

ethylene glycol (1 ml) as a crosslinking agent. The resulting precipitate was washed by methanol and water till free from unreacted dithizone-complex and dried. By using four different metal complexes four polymer-metal complex matrices were prepared by the above method.

The metal ions from the polymeric ligands thus prepared were extracted by 0.1 N HCl. The metal absorption capacities of different template polymer matrix were measured by treating the polymer with metal salts solutions and the metal ion contents analysed using standard 0.01 M EDTA solution. The amount of ligand attached to the polymers was estimated from nitrogen analysis.

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